

Syntheses and molecular structures of mononuclear copper(II) complex with pyridine-4-amidoxime and manganese(II) complex with 4-(2-pyridyl)-2,2':6',2''-terpyridine[†]

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Abstract : A Cu^{II} complex having the molecular formula [Cu(L1H)₂(NCS)₂].H₂O (1) was synthesized using L1H, CuCl₂.2H₂O and KSCN (L1H = pyridine-4-amidoxime). The Mn^{II} complex [Mn(L2)(NCS)(OAc)(H₂O)].H₂O (2) was synthesized using L2, Mn(OAc)₂.4H₂O and KSCN (L2 = 4'-(2-pyridyl)-2,2':6',2''-terpyridine). The molecular structures of 1 and 2 were established using single crystal X-ray crystallography. In 1, copper(II) ion has a distorted square planar geometry and also contain an unusual mode of coordination of pyridine-4-amidoxime, in which the pyridine nitrogen is coordinated while the amidoxime group remaining free. In 2, the central metal ion has a distorted pseudo octahedral geometry.

Keywords : Synthesis, copper(II), manganese(II), molecular structure, mononuclear.

Introduction

Amidoximes can be considered as an oxime^{1a} of amide and pyridine ring containing amidoxime was reported about 30 years ago^{1b}. Pyridine-2-amidoxime possesses the α , α' -diimidine moiety, $-N=C-C=N-$ and is similar to that present in 1,10-phenanthroline and 2,2'-bipyridyl. Amidoximes are known to co-ordinate in bi-²⁻⁴, tri-⁵, tetra-⁶ and hexa-dentate⁷ fashions. The presence of the amine functionality is special due to its (a) coordination capability, (b) potential for proton addition or removal and (c) offer different electronic property at oxime function. Also it can potentially involve in hydrogen bonding interactions when compared with corresponding oxime {(Py)C(R)NOH; R = H, Me, Ph, etc.}. Its 2-pyridyl, oxime and amino functionalities provide a rich potential for cluster formation as well.

Amidoximes also find technological applications, such as corrosion inhibition, stabilizing polymeric coating in

the development of chemical electronic micro sensors and uranium recovery from seawater. Amidoximes, especially those carrying arylsulfonyl and pyridyl, were reported to have significant biological activities such as : hypoglycaemic, analgesics, pesticides, herbicides and antihypertensives⁸. Use of amidoximes as ligands in synthesising 3d-metal molecular cluster are however comparatively limited⁹ and thus use of these kind of ligands either solely or in combination with other ligands remain important. Few amidoximes are utilized in the synthesis of first-row transition metal (in particular, manganese) clusters, which behave as single-molecule magnets (SMMs)^{10,11}. Complexes of pyridine-2-amidoxime of bis-chelated copper(II)^{12,13}, tris-chelated nickel(II)¹³, a cationic Ni^{II}₁₂ cluster¹⁴, single-decker [Ni₄(L1H)₂(L1)₂]²⁺ fragments¹⁵ were reported in the literature. Probable coordination modes of pyridine-2-amidoxime, its ionic forms viz. (Py)C(NH₂)NO⁻ and (Py)C(NH)NO²⁻, are as follows :

[†]In honour of Professor Animesh Chakravorty on the occasion of his 80th birth anniversary.

Polypyridyl complexes of transition metals have been extensively utilized as photo sensitizer and electron-relay species in photochemical system directed toward the conversion of solar energy¹⁶. Metal complexes of terpyridine and its derivatives have versatile applications, e.g. DNA binding ability¹⁷, cytostatic activity¹⁸, topoisomerase I inhibitory activity¹⁹, supramolecular chemistry²⁰, enantioselective synthesis²¹, fluorophores²², and photo induced light harvesting²³, and crystal engineering^{24–28}. Taking interest from the chemistry of amidoximes and polypyridyl ligands, synthesis and structural characterization of complexes of these two ligands were undertaken and results are reported here.

Scheme 1. Ligands.

Experimental

Instrumentation and methods :

X-Ray crystallographic data were collected using Bruker SMART APEX-CCD diffractometer with Mo K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$). The intensity data were corrected for Lorentz and polarization effects and empirical absorption corrections was applied using SAINT program^{29,30}. All the structures were solved by direct methods using SHELXS-97³¹. Non-hydrogen atoms located from the difference Fourier maps were refined anisotropically by full-matrix least-squares on F^2 , using SHELXL-97³¹. The hydrogen atoms were included in the calculated positions and refined isotropically using a riding model.

Syntheses :

Pyridine-4-amidoxime (**L1H**) and **L2**³² were prepared by adopting the reported procedures.

$[\text{Cu}(\text{L1H})_2(\text{NCS})_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**1**) :

To 45 mg (0.26 mmol) of $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ dissolved in 20 mL of methanol, 51 mg (0.52 mmol) of KSCN was added and stirred for 10 min. Then 36 mg of (0.26 mmol) **L1H** was added and stirred for another 1 h. The reaction mixture was left undisturbed and the green needle shaped crystals deposited after a week was collected by filtration after washing with ice-cold methanol and dried in desiccators. Yield 50 mg (35%). IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3315(b), 2106(s), 1647(s), 1617(s), 1545(m), 1419(m), 1382(s), 1218(s), 1062(s), 1024(m), 936(s), 837(s), 682(s), 527(m), 444(m); UV-Vis [λ_{max} , nm (ϵ , $\text{M}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$), CH_3OH solution] : 388(241), 289(1133).

$[\text{Mn}(\text{L2})(\text{NCS})(\text{OAc})(\text{H}_2\text{O})] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**2**) :

To a methanolic solution (40 mL) of **L2** (180 mg, 0.85 mmol), $\text{Mn}(\text{OAc})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (167 mg, 0.68 mmol) and KNCS (83 mg, 0.85 mmol) were added and stirred for 4 h. The resultant red-brown solution was left undisturbed. Dark crystals of **2** deposited after a week were collected after washing with ice-cold methanol. Yield : 300 mg (85%). IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : $\nu_{(\text{N}=\text{C})}$, 2074, 2054 and $\nu_{(\text{C}=\text{N})}$, 1605.

Results and discussion

Molecular structures :

The molecular structures of **1** and **2** were established using the single crystal X-ray diffraction methods. The crystallographic data and refinement parameters are listed in Table 1. Complex **1** crystallized in the $P2_1/n$ space groups. In this complex, the bivalent copper is bound by two **L1H** ligands and two thiocyanate ions. Thiocyanate ion is an ambidentate ligand which can coordinate either through nitrogen or sulphur ends. The two nitrogen (N_T)

Table 1. Crystallographic data and refinement parameters of compound **1** and **2**

	1	2
Formula	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ CuN ₈ O ₃ S ₂	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₄ SMn
Formula weight	472.00	518.45
<i>T</i> (K)	296(2)	296(2)
Wavelength (Å)	0.71073	0.71073
Crystal system	Monoclinic	Triclinic
Space group	<i>P</i> 2 ₁ / <i>c</i>	<i>P</i> 1̄
<i>a</i> (Å)	14.2517(16)	8.9728(7)
<i>b</i> (Å)	9.3197(14)	10.7006(8)
<i>c</i> (Å)	15.4090(19)	14.1414(11)
α (°)	90.00	70.945(6)
β (°)	107.624(9)	73.756(6)
γ (°)	90.00	65.521(5)
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	1950.6(4)	1151.44(15)
<i>Z</i>	4	2
Goodness-of-fit ^a on <i>F</i> ²	1.025	1.013
<i>R</i> ₁ ^b , <i>wR</i> ₂ ^c (<i>I</i> ≥ 2σ(<i>I</i>))	0.0464, 0.0300	0.0613, 0.2250
<i>R</i> ₁ ^b , <i>wR</i> ₂ ^c (all data)	0.0749, 0.0834	0.0613, 0.2250
^a GOF = [Σ[w(<i>F</i> ₀ ² - <i>F</i> _c ²) ²]/M - N] ^{1/2} (M = number of reflections, N = number of parameters refined).		
^b <i>R</i> ₁ = Σ <i>F</i> ₀ - <i>F</i> _c / Σ <i>F</i> ₀ .		
^c <i>wR</i> ₂ = [Σ[w(<i>F</i> ₀ ² - <i>F</i> _c ²) ²]/Σ[w(<i>F</i> ₀ ²) ²] ^{1/2} .		

end of two thiocyanate ion bind Cu^{II} in the *trans* fashion, bond lengths of Cu-N_T are 1.942(6), 1.917(6) Å and bond angle N_T-Cu-N_T is 177.16°. The two pyridyl nitrogen (N_P) are also bound to Cu^{II} ion in *trans* fashion with Cu-N_P bond length of 2.028(5), 2.042(5) Å and N_P-Cu-N_P bond angle of 174.67°. However, the amidoxime group of **L1H** remain free. Copper(II) centre has distorted square

planar geometry as a result of severe *John-Teller effect*, having a *trans*-(N_P)₂(N_T)₂ coordination environment. In this complex, the two Cu-N_T bonds are shorter than two Cu-N_P bonds. The ORTEP and hydrogen bonding interactions are shown in Figs. 1 and 2 respectively and selected bond parameters are listed in Table 2.

The packing reveals the presence of following *inter*-molecular H-bonding interactions involving free amidoxime group, lattice water and sulphur from thiocyanate ion, having the non-bonded distances : O1...O3, 2.700(7); O2...O3, 2.722(5); O3...N5, 2.874(6); O1...N6, 2.965(5) and S2...O3, 3.227(5) Å.

Compound **2** crystallized in the *P*-1 point group and an ORTEP diagram is displayed in Fig. 3. In this monohydrate, the crystal lattice consists of complex molecule [Mn(L2)(NCS)(OAc)(H₂O)] and the lattice H₂O molecule. The central manganese(II) ion is surrounded by the three nitrogen atoms of meridionally coordinating ligand **L2**, oxygen atom of a monodentate acetate ion, oxygen atom of a water molecule and the nitrogen atom of a thiocyanate ion. Hence the Mn²⁺ ion has distorted pseudo-octahedral coordination geometry and a (N_P)₃N_TO_AO_W {N_P = N-pyridyl; N_T = N-thiocyanate; O_A = O-acetate and O_W = O-water} coordination environment. Selected bond distances and angles are listed in Table 3. The three nitrogen atoms of **L2** and oxygen atom of acetate ion occupy the basal plane. The nitrogen atom of thiocyanate ion and oxygen atom of water molecule occupy the two axial sites. The NCS⁻ anions bind in a monodentate end-on linear fashion. Mn²⁺ is a borderline acid and NCS⁻ is

Fig. 1. ORTEP (30% probability) diagram of **1**.

Fig. 2. Hydrogen bonding interactions in 1.

Table 2. Selected bond distances (Å) and angles (°) in 1

Bond	Distance	Bond	Angle
Cu1-N8	1.917(6)	N8-Cu1-N7	177.1(2)
Cu1-N7	1.942(6)	N8-Cu1-N1	92.1(2)
Cu1-N1	2.028(5)	N7-Cu1-N1	89.7(2)
Cu1-N2	2.042(5)	N8-Cu1-N2	91.7(2)
S1-C13	1.611(8)	N7-Cu1-N2	86.7(2)
S2-C14	1.658(8)	N1-Cu1-N2	174.7(2)
O1-N3	1.433(5)	C5-N1-Cu1	121.9(5)
O2-N5	1.422(5)	C1-N1-Cu1	122.2(5)
N3-C6	1.275(7)	C11-N2-C7	116.4(6)
N4-C6	1.369(7)	C11-N2-Cu1	118.6(5)
N5-C12	1.270(7)	C7-N2-Cu1	124.9(5)
N6-C12	1.372(7)	C6-N3-O1	109.4(5)
N7-C13	1.155(6)	C12-N5-O2	108.9(5)
N8-C14	1.145(6)	C13-N7-Cu1	163.2(5)

Table 3. Selected bond distances (Å) and angles (°)

Mn1-N1	2.279(3)	N1-Mn1-N2	71.44(10)
Mn1-N2	2.227(3)	N2-Mn1-N3	71.21(10)
Mn1-N3	2.286(3)	N1-Mn1-N3	142.62(11)
Mn1-N5	2.159(4)	N1-Mn1-N5	90.77(13)
Mn1-O1	2.107(3)	N2-Mn1-N5	96.58(12)
Mn1-O3	2.273(3)	N3-Mn1-N5	94.91(13)
		N1-Mn1-O1	115.95(12)
		N1-Mn1-O3	89.46(11)
		N2-Mn1-O1	168.69(11)
		N2-Mn1-O3	85.35(10)
		N3-Mn1-O1	100.77(12)
		N3-Mn1-O3	86.09(10)
		N5-Mn1-O1	91.98(13)
		N5-Mn1-O3	178.02(12)
		O1-Mn1-O3	86.16(11)

Fig. 3. ORTEP (30% probability ellipsoids) diagram of 2.

an ambidentate base having hard-N and soft-S donor atoms. Coordination of NCS^- through N-atom is as per the HSAB principle.

The oxygen atom O7 of lattice water molecule is involved in hydrogen bonding interaction with manganese bound oxygen of acetate ion, having non-bonded distances of $\text{O1}\cdots\text{O7}$, 2.969(7) and $\text{O1}\cdots\text{O7}$, 2.952(8) Å. The uncoordinated oxygen atom of acetate ion is involved in hydrogen bonding interaction with manganese bound water molecule with a distance $\text{O2}\cdots\text{O3}$, 2.650(5) Å. The coordinated water molecule is also involved in hydrogen bonding with uncoordinated pyridyl nitrogen of another molecule with a non-bonded contact $\text{O3}\cdots\text{N4}$, 2.807(4) Å, as shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Hydrogen bonding interactions in **2**.

Conclusions

In summary, using pyridine-4-amidoxime a new copper(II) coordination complex have been synthesized. The copper(II) center has distorted square planner geometry. The complex shows an unusual mode of coordination of pyridine-4-amidoxime, in which the pyridine nitrogen is coordinated to bivalent copper and the amidoxime group remaining uncoordinated. A mononuclear manganese(II) complex of composition $[\text{Mn}(\text{L2})(\text{NCS})(\text{OAc})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ has been synthesized using 4'-(2-pyridyl)-2,2':6',2''-terpyridine. Manganese(II) ion has a distorted pseudo-octahedral coordination geometry and coordination of NCS^- occurs through N-atom. Hydrogen bonding interaction is present between the coordinated oxygen atom of the acetate ion with the lattice water and uncoordinated oxygen atom of the acetate ion with the metal bound water molecule.

Supplementary data

Crystallographic data of **1** and **2** have been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Center, numbers CCDC 1433676 and 1433675.

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